

SORSE Workshops: **FAIR4RS**

17 November 2020

Session 1 Breakout Room 2 Notes

Title: What does reusability mean for software?

Lead: Carlos Martinez

Participants: all

Q1: Why do we want to reuse software?

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Axel: **speed** up own research; increase **quality** of research by building on established tools

Matthias: To **reduce duplication** of effort and to maximise the availability of expertise.

Malin: To be able to check and verify existing results/publications

Malin: to make it easier to build new tools/toolboxes by incorporating other's existing code

Malin: we also want the software/code to be readable and understandable so that it can be translated (ideal)/converted (realistic) into different implementation languages

Malin: also, reusing the same code across a community gets more eyes on the bugs (there are always bugs)

Markus: **Avoid duplication**

Paula: because nobody wants to reinvent the wheel

Cunliang: to save resources, to avoid reinventing wheels

Teri: Avoid duplication of effort and ensure results (of running software on particular data) can be reproduced. Share core library of functions etc.

Anna-Lena: prevent people reinventing the wheel again and again, more efficient use of resources, less to maintain, ideally let the experts write the tools for their domain and let others benefit from that

Stephan: don't reinvent the wheel. Should lead to more quality for the one tool which does the one job. Having one tool for the job reduces mental load on the user, less tools to memorize.

Fotis: not re-invent the wheel. Ensure less bugs/issues. Follow best practices for a particular problem.

Morane: There is a difference between re-using and reusing, in the sense that we use the same tool or we reuse the actual research (algorithm, implementation, libraries) just a link to the reuse initiative: <https://reuse.software/>

Axel: how much of the re-using aspect (running the compiled executable) is already covered by the interoperability criteria? (Malin: I guess it depends on how we view containerizing stuff? E.g. if you can run it in a containerized environment, is that sufficient? Or should it work in all future environments with all the supporting software updated to current versions?)

Summary: avoiding duplication of efforts (reinventing wheels) -- how software is reused also affects the reusability requirements

Q2: What are the limitations to achieve this goal?

Teri: **No licensing**. Incomplete set of **dependencies**/system requirements. Lack of **documentation**. Difficult to install and then even when installed, it cannot easily be run. Time - not always possible/supported to have the time available to deal with the above.

Stephan Janosch: The amount of tools is too big. Finding the right tool for the job is the problem. Computers can't help me with that yet. Not enough usage of a common workflow language.

Markus: Issues/Problems with the code might be overtaken by others, the more complex a software is, the more difficult is it to build upon it, differences regarding the computational environment

Axel: Lack of appropriate **documentation**. Figuring out whether a certain tool does the job takes too much time (**cumbersome installation** / compilation).

Anna-Lena: lack of maintenance/**documentation**/support, in many cases probably due to lack of funding for sustaining research software

Matthias: Lack of incentive i.e. research funding. Difficult to find existing software that can do the task that needs to be done.

Morane: **License** is crucial for both proprietary and open source code to know what is possible, but having it open source or licensed doesn't mean the software can be used or re-used. Limitations are more about environment (hardware, OS, dependencies) and maintenance. We can refer to the phenomenon "**software collapse**" see [K. Hinsén](#).

Fotis: Not enough information for most tools - esp. regarding I/O limitations and dependencies.

Cunliang: hard to find the right tool, documentation/tutorial is lacking or incomplete

Findability, licensing, documentation, dependencies, resources

Transcribed comments:

<dependencies>

- Morane Gruenpeter: environment